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Double network laminarin-boronic/alginate dynamic bioink for 3D bioprinting cell-laden constructs

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Abstract

The design of dynamically crosslinked hydrogel bioinks for three-dimensional (3D) bioprinting is emerging as a valuable strategy to advance the fabrication of mechanically tuneable cell-laden constructs for 3D *in vitro* disease modelling and tissue engineering applications. Herein, a dynamic bioink comprising boronic acid-functionalised laminarin and alginate is explored for bioprinting 3D constructs under physiologically relevant conditions. The formulated bioink takes advantage of a double crosslinked network that combines covalent but reversible boronate ester bonds and ionic gelation via divalent cations. Moreover, it exhibits suitable rheological properties and improved mechanical features owing to its modular crosslinking chemistry, yielding stable constructs with user-programmable architecture. We explored such dynamic bioink as a supporting matrix for different cell classes, namely osteoblast precursors, fibroblasts and breast cancer cells. The resulting cell-laden bioprinted hydrogels display a homogeneous cell distribution post-printing and exceptional cell viability (> 90 %) that can be maintained for prolonged time periods in culture (14 days) for all cell lines. This simple and chemically versatile approach is envisaged to accelerate the development of multifunctional bioinks and contribute towards the fabrication of biomimetic 3D scaffolds with applicability in a wide range of predictive or exploratory biomedical platforms.

Keywords: 3D bioprinting, laminarin, boronic acid, alginate, dynamic bioink, double network hydrogel

1. Introduction

Three-dimensional (3D) bioprinting technologies have accelerated the development of complex hybrid structures with spatiotemporally defined organisation of biomaterials and living cells for numerous biomedical applications, including tissue engineering and *in vitro* disease modelling [1-3]. In this context, hydrogel bioinks have proven to be especially relevant since they can be engineered to confer the required hierarchy to produce multifunctional constructs capable of mimicking the structural complexity of tissues and providing suitable biochemical, mechanobiological, viscoelastic, stress-relaxing and/or topographical cues [4, 5].

Multiple biomaterials have been intensively explored in recent years concerning their ability to be processed using additive manufacturing techniques, such as extrusion, inkjet and laser-assisted printing, or stereolithography [6-10].

The biomaterial ink composition and mechanisms of network crosslinking play an important role on the mechanical, physicochemical and biological functions of the resulting 3D constructs. In fact, the properties required for cell survival and proliferation frequently conflict with those required for processability and printing fidelity [11, 12]. Mechanical forces exerted during this process, which depend on the shear stress, geometry and length of the needle, flow rate and viscosity of the bioink, can affect cellular viability [13, 14]. For example, cells laden in bioinks with low viscosity

tend to sediment at the bottom of the cartridge and thus result in inhomogeneous volumetric cellular distributions. On the contrary, increasing bioink viscosity may cause cell membrane disruption due to increased shear stress during the extrusion process [15, 16]. Importantly, shear sensitivity can vary with cell size, shape, and the inherent composition of its cytoskeleton, and thereby should be taken into consideration during bioink design stages. Such premises as: (i) obtaining a homogeneous cell suspension, (ii) avoiding cell damage, (iii) ensuring cellular hydration during the printing procedure, and (iv) assuring constructs mechanical stability under cell culture conditions, are essential for the reproducibility and translation of this technology towards numerous applications [17, 18].

In recent years, 3D bioprinting of cell-laden hydrogels employing dynamic networks has received significant emphasis since these materials can more closely mimic the permissive mechanics of the extracellular matrix (ECM) (i.e. viscoelasticity, stress relaxation and stiffness properties), while providing a responsive and biomimetic microenvironment for cell adhesion and proliferation under external stimuli conditions [19-22]. Dynamic bioinks can support the fabrication of adaptable hydrogels that are mechanically tuneable with superior printability and shape fidelity [20, 23]. Owing to their unique and dynamic chemistries, their networks can be disrupted when subjected to standalone or multifarious physicochemical spurs (e.g., shear forces, temperature, light, enzymes or redox) and rapidly reformed upon stimuli removal [24]. In addition, double crosslinked networks may be introduced to improve the stability and robustness of the bioprinted constructs, and concomitantly provide a suitable setting for biological systems to mature and become fully functional [17, 25-29].

Various types of hydrogel platforms with dynamic (covalent and noncovalent) crosslinking mechanisms have been proposed for 3D bioprinting, including supramolecular host-guest interactions, Schiff bases and hydrogen bonding, among others [6, 30-35]. However, very few studies have exploited intrinsically dynamic covalent boronate ester complexes to develop hydrogel bioinks [36, 37].

The use of boronic moieties for functionalisation of (bio)molecules is particularly attractive since they are able to readily react with naturally-occurring nucleophiles in aqueous conditions (without the need of catalysts) towards the complexation of vicinal hydroxyl groups, such as carbohydrates, polyols and catechols, which can selectively establish reversible covalent boronate ester bonds in a pH-dependent manner, besides being responsive to saccharides and reactive oxygen species (ROS) [38, 39]. To date, this chemistry has found diverse applications in the form of nanoparticles, hydrogels or membranes as electrochemical sensors, drug delivery systems, cell culture and cell capturing materials [40-45].

Polymers from natural origin, such as alginate, gelatin and hyaluronic acid, have been extensively exploited in 3D bioprinting owing to their versatility, biodegradability, biocompatibility, non-immunogenic properties and, in some cases, structural similarity to native tissue ECM [46-50]. Particularly, alginate (monovalent form of alginic acid) is a biocompatible and inexpensive polysaccharide whose anionic linear backbone comprises (1,4)-linked β -D-mannuronate (M-blocks) and α -L-guluronate (G-blocks) residues that can be crosslinked in the presence of divalent cations (e.g., Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+}) [51]. On the other hand, laminarin (also known as laminaran) is a relatively underexploited biodegradable and cytocompatible brown algae derived β -D-glucan that exhibits relevant immunomodulating, antioxidant and anticancer activities, with a considerably lower molecular weight when compared to alginate, which curbs its printability aptitude, but is prone to be chemically modified [52]. Recently, our group has been actively involved in exploring laminarin polymeric backbone to design dynamic covalently crosslinked hydrogels [35, 53].

In this work, we report the rapid fabrication of unique double crosslinked polysaccharide-based hydrogels using 3D extrusion bioprinting (Figure 1). The design rationale of the two-component network relies on a first crosslinking mechanism based on the covalent, albeit reversible, boronate ester complexes formation between the boronic acid motifs of laminarin (LAM-PBA) and the diol groups of alginate to develop a fully natural origin and easily processable dynamic bioink under physiological conditions. Thereafter, a secondary crosslinking step occurs following extrusion driven by the non-covalent alginate gelation with calcium ions to fabricate double network constructs, which ultimately improves their long-term strength, mechanics and use in culture [54]. These dynamic type of interactions within the bioink network are envisaged to: (i) prevent cellular sedimentation, and (ii) minimise the shear stress throughout

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the methodology to produce the dynamic bioink and manufacture cell-laden double network hydrogels through extrusion bioprinting. A dual-stage crosslinking strategy was employed: (i) establishment of dynamic covalent crosslinks *via* boronate esters formation between LAM-PBA and alginate (ALG) produces a shear-thinning bioink upon mixing of the two polymers and pre-osteoblasts, fibroblasts or cancer cells at physiological conditions; (ii) after printing, the ionic crosslinking between the guluronate groups in the alginate backbone and divalent calcium cations is promoted to generate a double network reinforced construct with tuneable mechanical properties.

the bioprinting process owing to its viscoelasticity, thus improving cell survival. To this end, the influence of printing parameters, bioink composition and cell density on the printability, rheological properties and cytocompatibility were systematically investigated. The proposed multi-component system design allows tuning double network hydrogels properties that are compatible with cellular encapsulation and long-term culture, which renders this platform amenable to a range of tissue engineering and 3D *in vitro* modelling applications.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

All reagents and solvents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck) unless otherwise stated and used as supplied. Alginic acid sodium salt (M_w 10 000 - 600 000 g mol⁻¹) (Panreac), alizarin red S (ARS), 3-aminophenylboronic acid hydrochloride (PBA; 98 %) (Alfa Aesar), calcium chloride (CaCl₂; anhydrous, > 96 %), deuterium oxide (D₂O; 99.9 % D) (Cambridge Isotope Laboratories), Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM), ethylene glycol (≥ 99%), D-glucose (Fluka), glycine (> 99%), laminaran from *Eisenia bicyclis* (TCI Chemicals), methanol (Fisher), formaldehyde solution (PFA), phosphate buffered saline (PBS), sodium bicarbonate, sodium borohydride (> 95 %) (TCI Chemicals), sodium metaperiodate (98 %) (Alfa Aesar) and Triton™ X-100. Antibiotic-antimycotic solution (100x), heat-inactivated

foetal bovine serum (FBS, South America origin), LIVE/DEAD® cell viability kit, Minimum Essential Medium alpha (α -MEM) and trypanLE™ express solution were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific. CellTiter-Glo® 3D cell viability assay was purchased from Promega.

2.2. Synthesis and characterisation of LAM-PBA

Phenylboronic acid-modified laminarin (LAM-PBA) was synthesised *via* a two-step reaction according to a previously procedure [53]. Initially, laminarin (500 mg, 0.617 mmol) and sodium periodate (440 mg, 2 mmol) were dissolved in 5 mL of ultrapure water. The mixture was left at room temperature (RT) in the dark for 5 h under magnetic stirring and ethylene glycol (117 μ L, 2.1 mmol) was then added to quench the reaction. The resultant biopolymer exhibited an oxidation degree of *ca.* 52 % [35], was purified by dialysis against deionised water for 3 days, at RT, and then freeze-dried (-80 °C; Telstar LyoQuest). Partially oxidized laminarin (190 mg, 0.234 mmol) and 3-aminophenylboronic acid hydrochloride (76 mg, 0.438 mmol) were then dissolved in ultrapure water (8 mL) and stirred for 30 min before sodium borohydride (166 mg, 4.39 mmol), in methanol (800 μ L), was added to the flask. The reaction was carried out for 8 h in the dark at RT. Finally, the reaction mixture was dialysed against water (MWCO 3.5 kDa, Spectrum™ Spectra/Por™ 3) and freeze-dried to obtain the polymer product as a pink-coloured powder (yield ~84 %; SEC M_n 6230 Da and PDI ~1.77).

Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR) spectra were acquired on a 300 MHz Bruker Avance III spectrometer and analysed using MestReNova software v6.0.2; tetramethylsilane (TMS) was used as an internal reference. The molecular weight of the polymer was determined using size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) equipped with a refractive index detector (Viscotek). The system was equipped with an on-line degasser and the chromatograms were recorded at 30 °C. The mobile aqueous phase was set at a flow rate of 1 mL \cdot min $^{-1}$ and poly(ethylene glycol) standards were used for calibration. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed using a TGA-50 instrument (Shimadzu). After stabilisation, the samples were heated from 20 to 700 °C at a ramp rate of 5/10 °C \cdot min $^{-1}$ under a flow of nitrogen.

2.3. Alizarin Red S fluorescence assay

A stock solution of alizarin red S (ARS) (0.1 mM, pH 7.4) was prepared in PBS, and LAM-PBA, laminarin or alginate were dissolved at a concentration of 5 mg \cdot mL $^{-1}$. The fluorescence intensity spectra (excitation wavelength at 465 nm, 0.5 nm step) were acquired at RT using a quartz cuvette in a Jasco FP-8300 spectrophotometer. The degree of substitution was quantified *via* ARS well-established competitive assay based on a calibration curve using 3-aminophenylboronic acid as the standard molecule, and taking into account that PBA ratio was 0.4.

2.4. Dynamic biomaterial ink formulation and printing

3D printing of the biomaterial inks was performed in an INKREDIBLE+ (CELLINK co.) dual-head extrusion 3D bioprinter under aseptic conditions. LAM-PBA and alginate (ALG) were dissolved separately in PBS (pH 7.4) to obtain 5-10 % (w/v) and 3-5 % (w/v) solutions, respectively. Both precursor solutions were mixed at equal volume ratios and mechanically stirred at RT to ensure a homogeneous formulation within seconds (LAM-PBA_{2.5-5}/ALG_{1.5-2.5}). The biomaterial inks were freshly prepared, loaded into 3 mL cartridges, closed with pistons to prevent leaking. A 23 G nozzle was used for all experiments; the extrusion pressure was in the range of 80 kPa to 100 kPa and the speed of the printing head was set to 10 mm \cdot s $^{-1}$. The initial pressure was set by observing the flow of the material out of the needle in a stationary position to produce a continuous and uniform printable filament followed by diameter measurements to assess printability and shape fidelity. 3D printing was automatically performed into 12-well plates (pre-generated G-code) by printing CAD designed disk-shaped or spiral constructs with a diameter of 10 mm \times 0.4 mm (1 layer). Calcium chloride (CaCl₂; 10 mM) solution was then sprayed

onto each construct to promote the secondary ionic crosslinking, and consequently double network formation. Tubular 3D structures (at least 8 layers, $d = 10$ mm) were fabricated through an ionic-mediated sequential crosslinking strategy that involved multiple layer deposition and sprayed CaCl₂ crosslinking steps [55]. The resultant cell-laden constructs were then washed with PBS and placed in culture under controlled temperature and atmosphere conditions (37 °C, 5 % CO₂) for further studies. Biofabricated constructs' structure was imaged after printing through high resolution digital micrographs. ImageJ software (National Institutes of Health, USA) was used to quantify filaments diameter at different sections ($n=10$).

Hydrogels' microstructure was examined by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and the analysis was conducted on a HR-FESEM SU-70 instrument (Hitachi). Prior to examination, the samples were freeze-dried, cross-sectioned, mounted in aluminium stubs and sputter-coated with gold/palladium.

2.5. Rheological and mechanical characterisation

Rheological experiments of the formulated biomaterials were conducted in a Kinexus lab+ rotational rheometer (Malvern Instruments) fitted with a stainless-steel parallel plate geometry (8 mm), at RT, using a solvent trap. Oscillatory strain amplitude sweep measurements were performed at 1 Hz to determine the linear viscoelastic region (LVR). Oscillatory frequency sweep experiments were conducted at a constant 1 % strain to determine the storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli, and $\tan \delta$ (G''/G'). Shear rate ramp tests were carried out to evaluate the shear-thinning profile. Three samples were used for each run and the average results are reported (experiments show hydrogels' properties with and without MC3T3-E1 cells).

Mechanical properties of the double network hydrogels were evaluated using a Universal Mechanical Testing System (Instron[®] 3340 series) equipped with a 1 kN load cell. Compression tests were conducted on cylindrical samples with an average diameter of 6 mm and height of 5 mm, after 1 h, at RT, after applying a pre-load of 0.01 N. The compression rate was set at constant 0.5 mm \cdot min $^{-1}$. The compressive or Young's modulus (E) corresponding to the average slope of the stress-strain curve in the linear region (from 0 % to 15 % strain) was then extrapolated.

2.6. Water content determination and swelling behaviour

The water content in the freshly prepared hydrogels ($n = 3$) was assessed at 24 h incubation by measuring the wet sample

weight (W_w) and the dry sample weight (D_w) after freeze-drying, and calculated according to the equation:

$$\text{Water content (\%)} = \frac{W_w - D_w}{W_w} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

To assess the swelling behaviour of the LAM-PBA₅/ALG_{2.5} gels in a concentrated glucose solution (28 mM) over time, freshly prepared constructs were first weighted (W_0), immersed in the media and incubated at 37 °C (in static conditions). At specific time intervals, the samples were wiped gently with blotting paper and finally weighted (W_f). The hydrogel weight change with respect to time was determined according to the formula:

$$\% \text{weight change} = \frac{W_f - W_0}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

2.7. Cell culture and 3D bioprinting

Pre-osteoblastic MC3T3-E1 cells (ATCC[®] CRL-2593[™]), L929 fibroblasts (ECACC 85011425) and adenocarcinoma MDA-MB-231 cells (ATCC[®] CRM-HTB-26[™]) were cultured at 37 °C under a 5 % CO₂ humidified atmosphere in α -MEM, DMEM-LG and DMEM-HG, respectively, supplemented with 10 % (v/v) FBS and 1 % antibiotic-antimycotic solution (penicillin, streptomycin and amphotericin B). The cells were passaged every 2-3 days upon reaching confluency, and reseeded prior to use.

Prior to all 3D bioprinting assays, the solutions were sterilized by filtration using a 0.22 μ m filter or by exposure to UV light for 15 min at RT. LAM-PBA₅/ALG_{2.5} hydrogel formulations were prepared as described earlier. MC3T3-E1 cells were suspended in the biomaterial ink at various densities: 1×10^6 , 2.5×10^6 and 5×10^6 cells per mL. L929 and MDA-MB-231 were encapsulated at densities of 2×10^6 cells·mL⁻¹. Then, the bioinks were immediately loaded into the printing cartridges and transferred to the 3D bioprinter to initiate the manufacturing process, performed under sterile conditions at RT. The cell-laden gels (prepared in triplicate) were incubated at 37 °C and 5 % CO₂ in complete culture media (replaced every 2-3 days) up to 14 days.

2.8. Cell viability assays

The viability of the encapsulated cells, at different time points, was evaluated by a Live/Dead fluorescent assay. Cell-laden gels were labelled with calcein-AM/propidium iodide (PI) in PBS (according to the manufacturer's protocol) for 30 min, at 37 °C and then washed with PBS. The constructs were imaged in a Zeiss Imager M2 widefield fluorescence microscope equipped with a 3.0 Mpix camera and a 10x/0.4 Plan-Neofluar objective, or in a Zeiss LSM 880 Airyscan confocal laser scanning microscope equipped with GaAsP and PMT

detectors and a 10x/0.4 Plan-Apochromat objective (Carl Zeiss Microscopy, GmbH, Germany). The data were processed in ZEN blue edition (SP3) and Imaris[®] software. Microscopy images were analysed with Adobe Photoshop to quantify the ratio of viable cells in the different hydrogels as a function of green and red pixels (channels) intensities. ImageJ was used to quantify the number of cells on each quadrant of the x - y plane (height of 700 μ m) of the confocal microscopy images.

Metabolic activity of L929 cells was determined based on ATP quantification using a CellTiter-Glo luminescent cell viability assay optimised for 3D cultures in agreement to the manufacturer's instructions. Cell-laden constructs and controls were incubated for *ca.* 30 min with an equal volume of DMEM and reagent kit, after homogenisation, and protected from light at RT. Luminescence was read on 96-well white bottom plates by using a multimodal microplate reader (Synergy HTX, BioTek Instruments).

2.9. Statistical analysis

The data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) from triplicates and analysed using GraphPad software (v6.0). The statistical significance of the differences was evaluated by either one-way (comparison between multiple groups) or two-way (comparison of grouped data) ANOVA analyses. Prior to this, the homogeneity of variances and normality distribution criteria were assessed. The level of significance was set at * $p \leq 0.05$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis and characterisation of LAM-PBA

Laminarin extracted from *Eisenia bicyclis* seaweed is a biocompatible and chemically versatile β -glucan with (1,3) and (1,6) glycosidic bonds in the main chain and occasional (1,6) side chain branches, comprising mannitol or glucose units on the reducing ends at different ratios [56], which allows for diverse intrachain modifications. Herein, this polysaccharide was chemically functionalised with PBA groups by a two-step oxidation-coupling reaction and characterised by ¹H NMR and SEC. The periodate-mediated oxidation of laminarin enables the successful insertion of amine-containing PBA motifs in the polymer backbone, as confirmed by the presence of the typical aromatic peak of PBA at $\delta = 7.0$ -7.5 ppm in the NMR spectrum [53] (Figure S1, Supporting Material). As determined by SEC analysis, the molecular weight of LAM-PBA following chemical modification was approximately 6.2 kDa (Figure S2A).

A more detailed insight of the presence and quantification of PBA groups in the backbone of laminarin was demonstrated

by performing a fluorescence binding assay based on the diol-containing dye alizarin red S (ARS). ARS adduct becomes strongly fluorescent upon binding with boronic acid residues establishing a dynamic equilibrium [57]. Mixing of LAM-PBA with ARS in PBS buffer resulted in the formation of boronate ester complexes, which was confirmed by the notable increase in the fluorescence intensity around $\lambda_{Em} = 557$ nm, presented in Figure 2. Boronic acid group content in the polymer was approximately 21 ± 1.4 % as determined from the standard curve (Figure S2B). Control experiments showed negligible increase in fluorescence maximum upon interaction of unmodified laminarin and alginate with ARS, highlighting the specific boronate-ARS interaction.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) curves (Figure S2C, D) reveal that LAM-PBA exhibits a three-stage mass loss, one minor from 20-90 °C due to the moisture and other volatiles, followed by a sharp mass loss with onset around 240 °C, characteristic of laminarin backbone degradation, which is completed at 460 °C, and a third stage of lower mass loss rate from 510 to 620 °C (*ca.* 10 %). Hence, the difference in thermal stability between unmodified and modified laminarin

Figure 2. Fluorescence spectra of LAM-PBA, LAM-PBA/ALG, pristine laminarin and alginate upon interaction with ARS in PBS ($\lambda_{ex}=465$ nm).

can be attributed to the decomposition of aminophenylboronic acid residues [58] that are present in the former biopolymer.

Pristine laminarin, owing to its low molecular weight, has poorly suited rheological properties for extrusion, which in turn can be offset by chemical modification with boronic acid moieties and subsequent dynamic covalent crosslinking with alginate to enhance the biomaterial ink overall viscosity.

Figure 3. (A) Phase diagram and printing conditions tested for optimal ink development in terms of printability, extrudability and homogeneity. (B) Digital photographs and bright-field micrograph of LAM-PBA₅/ALG_{2.5} disk-shaped cell-laden constructs illustrating the strut concentric pattern still evident after 3 days in culture (I); fluorescence microscopy conjugated with bright-field imaging of MC3T3-E1 cells within LAM-PBA₅/ALG_{2.5} hydrogel following live/dead staining (II; green channel: calcein AM, red channel: PI). (C) 3D bioprinting of well-defined solid filaments with a spiral pattern. Optical microscopy images demonstrate smooth filaments with constant diameter post-printing and crosslinking (I, II); micrograph of live/dead staining of MDA-MB-231 cells in a printed filament 7 days post-bioprinting (III). (D) Bioprinted tubular construct demonstrating the potential of the bioink to fabricate 3D structures.

Figure 4. Dynamic rheological characterisation of LAM-PBA₅/ALG_{2.5} gels (pH 7.4, RT). Frequency sweep at a strain of 1 % of (A) single network ALG₃ and double crosslinked LAM-PBA₅/ALG_{2.5} hydrogels without cells at day 1, and (B) cell-laden gels after 7 days in culture. (C) Viscosity of the gel-phase bioinks with different cell concentrations as function of shear rate, demonstrating a shear-thinning behaviour.

3.2. Dynamic bioink formulation and printing of 3D constructs

An optimal window of bioink viscoelasticity (i.e. flow and shape retention) is one of the most crucial factors to consider in extrusion-based 3D bioprinting. Therefore, preliminary screening of LAM-PBA/ALG formulations with different polymer concentrations and ratios was performed to identify the most suitable hydrogel ink composition for printing, using the minimum biopolymer content, at which consistent and continuous filaments could be formed (at the tip of the nozzle), in a reproducible and controlled mode, maintaining the pre-designed shape from the instant immediately after extrusion until it is ionically crosslinked [12, 59] (Figure 3A). We observed that the printability of the biomaterials were also dependent on various parameters, including path height, needle geometry, applied pressure and printing speed, as detailed in the experimental section (~90 kPa, 23 G and 10 mm·s⁻¹).

To rapidly prepare the biomaterial inks, equivalent ratios of precursor solutions of LAM-PBA 10 % (w/v) and alginate 5 % (w/v) were simply mixed at physiological pH and room temperature, and then loaded into the cartridge, which allows to form dynamic covalent boronate ester bonds (first network) between boronic acid pendant groups of laminarin and the diols from alginate backbone. As previously mentioned, PBA and diol-containing molecules establish a dynamic equilibrium to form boronate ester bonds. Hence, the complex formation was investigated by optimising the PBA-ARS affinity assay to measure the variation of the fluorescence intensity and, therefore, assess the availability of free groups for binding. As observed in Figure 2, a steep decrease was observed, suggesting the majority of the boronic acid groups were involved in the establishment of the dynamic crosslinks between LAM-PBA and alginate.

The structural integrity and fidelity (3D geometry) of the biomaterial ink filaments were well-preserved as demonstrated when extruding uniform spiral patterns (strut width *ca.* 1.2 mm) and disk-shaped constructs (*d* = 10 mm), Figures 3B, C. Following the printing step, a calcium chloride solution was homogeneously sprayed to promote alginate ionic

crosslinking (second network), enabling the preparation of well-defined constructs with a reinforced double network, which exhibit a characteristic reddish colour. Furthermore, a bottom-up approach based on LAM-PBA₅/ALG_{2.5} biomaterial ink sequential deposition/spray-mediated ionic crosslinking step was employed to produce a free-standing and robust 3D tubular architecture (Figure 3D and Video S1).

The water content average values of the double crosslinked hydrogel formulations ranged from 91 % to 96 % (Figure S3A), which makes them interesting scaffolds for applications that mimic biological tissues requiring high water content [60]. Hence, the increase in polymer concentration led to a slight decrease of the water content that might result from the higher crosslinking degree of the network. The ability to prepare hydrogels with a slow degradation profile is essential to guarantee robust polymer matrices with long-term stability for cell encapsulation applications taking into account the sugar-sensitive nature of this boronate type of crosslinking. After incubating LAM-PBA₅/ALG_{2.5} gels in a concentrated glucose solution at physiological pH (analogous to high glucose cell culture medium), the constructs showed a moderate swelling behaviour in the first 6 days followed by a plateau (maintaining their pre-incubation dimensions), which highlights their adequate tolerance to high glucose content of the medium (Figure S3B). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs of freeze-dried hydrogels show an interconnected highly porous internal network microstructure, as depicted in Figure S3C, D.

3.3. Rheological and mechanical properties

The viscoelastic properties of the materials were evaluated by dynamic rheology measurements. First, oscillatory strain sweeps were carried out to determine the linear viscoelastic region of the LAM-PBA₅/ALG_{2.5} hydrogel. The elastic storage (*G'*) and loss (*G''*) shear moduli were found to intersect at a critical strain of approximately 10 %, i.e. network rupture, that result from the tight network formed (Figure S4A); below this value, the samples behave linearly viscoelastic so the amplitude for frequency sweeps was chosen to be 1 %. Throughout the frequency sweep experiments, *G'* was

consistently higher than G'' , as shown in Figure 4A, where both curves were parallel and nearly independent of the frequency ($G' \sim 12$ kPa); in addition, the constant loss tangent profile $\tan \delta < 1$ demonstrates that the elastic regime of the material dominates across the frequency range, which demonstrates the strong and stable nature of the crosslinking network (gel-like character). Interestingly, the dynamic bioink displays a typical frequency-dependent viscoelastic behaviour before the ionic crosslinking (evidenced by the crossover of G' and G''), with a lower elastic strength but fast network relaxation time ($\tau < 1$ s) [61], Figure S4B. This dual-stage crosslinking approach can therefore strengthen the mechanical support to preserve the architecture of the 3D bioprinted structures and improve their rheological properties (increase of elastic modulus) compared to control alginate single network hydrogels (Figure 4A).

Biological tissues display a plethora of cell densities depending on the organs or anatomical subsections. Also, as anticipated, the efficiency of cell-based therapeutic modalities strongly depend on the cell concentration administered [62]. Therefore, it is important to assess the feasibility of the bioprintable formulations and benchmark them over an array of cell densities to leverage their potential for translational biomedical applications. In order to study the effect of encapsulated cells on the rheological properties of the hydrogels, we sought to perform frequency sweep tests on LAM-PBA₅/ALG_{2.5} ensembles with different concentrations of MC3T3-E1 cells 7 days post-incubation, Figure 4B. Elastic and viscous moduli of the hydrogels were quantitatively compared (as a measure of the gel strength), and their values at the plateau gradually dropped from 1160 to 355 Pa and 92 to 21 Pa, respectively, when the number of encapsulated cells increased from 1×10^6 to 5×10^6 cells·mL⁻¹ (Figure S4C); as expected, these results suggest that cell encapsulation elicits a lower crosslinking density per gel weight where cells can act as “soft particle fillers”, which somewhat weakens the gel original network [13, 63]. Furthermore, hydrogels during long term culture periods may release ions through passive diffusion into the media, leading to the disintegration of ionic crosslinks, and consequent residual loss of mechanical integrity, although they could still perfectly withstand their shape/structure.

The shear-thinning response of the bioinks was investigated by monitoring the viscosity changes with the shear rate, as displayed in Figure 4C. The flow curves reveal a power-law decrease of the viscosity of all samples with increasing shear rate, which allow for low resistance during injection, even though their viscosity magnitude was slightly affected by cellular concentration.

LAM-PBA₅/ALG_{2.5} gels were also subject to uniaxial compression tests and exhibited an average compressive modulus that was superior to the corresponding LAM₅/ALG_{2.5} control only crosslinked through ionic gelation, as depicted in

Figure S4D, suggesting a reinforcing effect provided by the existence of the double crosslinked network. We are thus able to precisely control the fabrication of defined structures with tuneable mechanical properties, possessing a Young's modulus (10.61 ± 1.54 kPa) comparable to the range of native soft tissues [64]. The development of such dynamic bioinks has a significant impact on 3D bioprinting applications contributing to manufacture constructs with adaptable biomechanical properties and biodegradability, while might also allowing them to operate as responsive supporting scaffolds during cell culture.

3.4. *In vitro* cytocompatibility of cell-laden gels

The impact of the 3D printing process on the viability of the cells embedded in the bioink and the possibility to explore it as a (double crosslinked) generic supporting matrix was investigated. MC3T3-E1 (osteoblast precursor), L929 (fibroblast) and MDA (breast carcinoma) were selected as model cell lines to demonstrate the versatility and compatibility of the bioink in various cell types.

Figure 5. (A) Representative merged fluorescence micrographs from the live/dead assays (green/red, respectively) of encapsulated MC3T3-E1, L929 and MDA-MB-231 cells within the LAM₅/ALG_{2.5} hydrogels at different incubation time points from 3 to 14 days (scale bars: 200 μm). Negligible cell death was observed for all conditions. (B) Quantification of cellular viability post-printing. The data are expressed as mean ± SD of at least three selected images for each condition, and no significant differences were found between time points. (C) Metabolic activity of encapsulated L929 at different time points determined by the 3D CellTiter-Glo[®] luminescent viability assay (mean ± SD from triplicates; **p≤0.01 and ***p≤0.001). (D) Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) images showing the cellular spatial arrangement within the bioprinted cell-laden gels at day 7 of culture (3D reconstruction). (E) Analysis of MC3T3-E1 cellular distribution in each quadrant of the *x-y* projection view of CLSM images *via* maximum intensity projection after 7 days (mean ± SD, *n*=3; *n/s*).

The resultant cell-laden gels were imaged by fluorescence microscopy, using the Live/dead staining, and representative images are displayed in Figures 5A after 3, 7 and 14 days in culture. Viability studies showed that encapsulated all cells, which exhibited a strong green fluorescent signal, remained viable for up to 14 days in culture post-printing without major aggregates. These results corroborate cells tolerance to the shear forces exerted during the printing process and the cell-protective quality of the herein developed biomaterial inks, possibly attributed to the preponderant behaviour of the dynamic covalent boronate crosslinks [23]. Remarkably, a high cell viability, above 90 % on average, was found during the entire incubation period of 14 days (Figure 5B) with no

statistical significance among the three cell lines. Moreover, metabolic activity results of encapsulated fibroblasts corroborate their long-term cell survival rate (Figure 5C).

High-resolution confocal microscopy 3D reconstructed images acquired clearly show that cellular distribution along the *z*-axis of the hydrogels was virtually independent of the depth (up to 800 μm), with no significant sedimentation being observed (Figure 5D). This property is increasingly desirable when designing a bioink as printing times of full-scale tissues may become a limitation (i.e. several hours). As shown in Figure 5E, a homogenous cell dispersion within the construct was obtained post-printing and ionic crosslinking.

4. Conclusions

The development of dynamic biomaterial inks from natural origin polymers that provide a suitable 3D microenvironment for cellular attachment holds potential for diverse bio-applications in the future, albeit their widespread use still poses several technical challenges. This led us to combine the chemical versatility of laminarin-boronic acid and alginate printing features for the first time to fabricate cell-laden double network constructs encompassing dynamic covalent and ionic networks.

In summary, we have designed a unique two-component polysaccharide-based dynamic hydrogel bioink using a dual-stage crosslinking strategy at physiological pH, which guarantees a homogeneous cell suspension and averts cell damage throughout the bioprinting process. The constructs can be printed directly onto the printing bed without the need of heating/cooling modules, or in-print UV curing. The pre-mixed LAM-PBA/ALG dynamic covalent boronate crosslinked network enables the bioink to be rapidly and precisely extruded, while the secondary calcium-mediated ionic crosslinking step endows the hydrogels with improved 3D processability, mechanical behaviour and stability during prolonged culture time. The rheological properties of the bioinks could also be tuned by varying the concentration of the polymeric components involved in the network formation, as well as the number of embedded cells. Cell viability analysis showed that MC3T3-E1, L929 and MDA-MB-231 cells remained viable (over 90 %) after bioprinting for at least 14 days in culture, presenting a homogeneous cell distribution, while surviving the mechanical stress and pressure exerted on their membranes during the process, which illustrate the bioink capability to provide a suitable microenvironment to maintain cellular functions. It is important to emphasise that boronic acid grafting in laminarin's backbone is not only a key component for the establishment of the dynamic covalent bonds, but such linkages are also recognised to be sensitive to numerous biological stimuli (e.g., glucose, pH and ROS), which provides an additional level of bio-responsiveness to the fabricated 3D constructs. Moreover, the secondary crosslinking step applied is user-definable as it can be performed during printing, or at the end of the process, which augments materials manufacturing prospects. Despite the promising results, further adjustments in the mechanical properties, and incorporation of growth factors/bioactive peptides may be considered to further improve cell adhesion and proliferation.

Overall, on the base of its simplicity, cytocompatibility and versatility, this bioink formulation holds promise to generate complex yet dynamic multicomponent scaffolds for a myriad of applications, including 3D *in vitro* disease modelling, therapeutics delivery and regenerative medicine.

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